

The Use of Teaching Aids in Increasing Student Motivation at Elementary School 027 Samarinda Ulu, East Kalimantan

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The Use of Teaching Aids in Increasing Student Motivation at Elementary School 027 Samarinda Ulu, East Kalimantan

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the role of the use of teaching aids by teachers in increasing student motivation at Elementary School 027 Samarinda Ulu in the 2019/2020 learning year. The technique of determining the subject used in this research was purposive sampling and the data analysis techniques used data collection, data selection, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. The type of triangulation used is source triangulation.

The result of the research is that the teacher uses teaching aids that are two-dimensional and three-dimensional. The increase in learning motivation for grade 1B students is good, this is evidenced by the willingness of students to bring props, increasing the enthusiasm of students to improve their lack of grades, increasing the focus of student learning, the enthusiasm of students in demonstrating directly the use of teaching aids.

Keywords: Teaching Aids, Learning Motivation

INTRODUCTION

Education is a way of obtaining knowledge consciously and planned. Education is classified into three, namely formal education, non-formal education and informal education. Formal education, namely participating in the teaching and learning process in schools that are structured and tiered consisting of primary education, secondary education and higher education. Non-formal education is obtained from the learning process outside the school environment. Meanwhile, informal education is obtained from within the family and the environment such as courtesy, morals, ethics and

others. Everyone needs education to free himself or a nation from the pain of ignorance, poverty and backwardness (Sagala, 2010)

Education in Indonesia currently uses the 2013 curriculum is identical to thematic learning and integrated learning. The concept of thematic learning is to use a theme to connect several subjects, so that it can add meaningful knowledge and experience to students. One theme is divided into four sub-themes and one sub-theme is divided into six lessons. Teachers are required to be creative in developing the lessons on the theme so that learning is not boring (Prastowo, 2019)

The role of a teacher, especially in formal education, is to educate, teach, guide, direct, motivate, train, assess and evaluate students. Teachers must have skills in selecting and using teaching aids in delivering learning material. The existence of teaching aids as a tool for teachers in delivering material so that students do not get bored when participating in the process of teaching and learning activities (Purbaningsih, 2017).

The focus of student learning can be stimulated by the use of media or props. Props are objects that are used to help the teaching and learning process. The use of teaching aids in the learning process can make teacher explanation methods more varied. The use of teaching aids can make students more active in participating in learning activities, demonstrate props and enthusiasm for learning (Purbaningsih, 2017) argues that the use of teaching aids can help teachers in delivering subject matter, can create a pleasant learning atmosphere for students, can motivate students to take part in learning. The use of teaching aids aims to increase student motivation and learning outcomes through the use of concrete teaching aids (Rahayu, 2018). The use of letter card props aims to improve student motivation and learning outcomes (Sarimani, 2016), besides that the use of graphic props can also increase student learning motivation (Nomleni, 2018)

Motivation to learn is a desire that arises from within and from outside a person. The strength and weakness of student participation in learning depends on how strong their motivation to learn. The stronger the student's motivation to learn, the stronger the effort and participation made in learning. Conversely, if the motivation to learn is weak, the effort and participation in learning will be weaker. Learning motivation is very important to be improved, this requires the role of various elements involved in the learning process both from students, teachers and the learning environment. If teachers are able to create learning situations that

exploit students' abilities, student perceptions that learning is a boring learning activity will be lost and learning objectives will be easier to achieve (Kusiah, 2015).

Based on the results of the observations described above, the researcher is interested in conducting research on the use of teaching aids in increasing the motivation of Class 1B students at the elementary school 027 Samarinda Ulu.

METHODS

This research was conducted to determine the role of teaching aids on student learning motivation. This type of research used in this research is qualitative research. Qualitative research is descriptive in nature and the nature of the research is natural. This research was conducted at Elementary School 027 Samarinda Ulu, Pramuka Street, Samarinda Ulu District, Samarinda City, East Kalimantan Province. This research was conducted in the even semester of the 2019/2020 learning year.

The research subjects in this study were class 1B teachers, five student form 1B class and five parents of student form 1B class. The sample selection in this research was using purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling technique is a technique of sampling data sources with certain considerations that the person know best what we expect (Sugiyono, 2016)

The criteria for the subject to be researched at class 1B teachers who had used teaching aids when teaching. The criteria for student subject are students who take part in teaching and learning activities in class 1B. The criteria for parent's student are parents who understand their child's personality.

The data collection techniques are interviews and documentation. There are four analysis techniques in qualitative research namely data collection, data selection, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. Data collection tools using interview guidelines and document guidelines. instrument validity testing is done by examining the validity of the content and validity of construct. The triangulation used in this study is the triangulation of sources (Sukardi, 2002)

RESULT

Based on the results of an interview with Mrs. JL as a grade 1B teacher at Elementary School 027 Samarinda Ulu on Monday, April 27,

2020 that in the learning process in class 1B using visual aids such as pictures. As for the lessons of Cultural Arts and Crafts, teachers sometimes use audio props such as loudspeakers. Audio-visual props such as videos are also used, but only Islamic teachers have applied these props. The props most often used be pictures because they are not only interesting but also easy to make.

Based on the results of interviews with a class 1B student named AR at SDN 027 Samarinda Ulu on Tuesday, April 28, 2020 that teachers often use picture props and have also used audio props, namely speakers, but never use video or films. The teaching aid most often used by teachers is pictures. This is the same as the results of interviews with FW students on Wednesday, April 29, 2020 that teachers teach using enlarged image and writing props and have also used audio props, namely speakers, but if audio-visual props such as videos or films have never been . The teaching aids most often used by teachers when teaching are pictures.

This is also the same as the results of interviews with ZP students on Thursday, April 30, 2020 that teachers teach using picture props, speakers are also ordinary but not often. The teaching aids most often used by the teacher are pictures. This is also the same as the results of interviews with AY students on Thursday, April 30, 2020 that teachers often use picture props and have also used speakers. Likewise the results of interviews with LV students on Thursday, April 30, 2020 that teachers often teach using picture props and have also used speakers. The props most often used be pictures.

Based on the results of the interviews and review of the documents above. It can be concluded that the teacher uses visual aids such as pictures, origami paper, number cards and has also used speakers when teaching in class. The teaching aids most often used by teachers when teaching are pictures

Benefits of Teaching Aids

Based on the results of an interview with Mrs. JL as grade 1B teacher at Elementary School 027 Samarinda Ulu on Monday, April 27, 2020 that the use of audio or visual aids in learning is quite effective, but the use of audio-visuals is more effective if the facilities are supportive. Teaching aids can make it easier for the teacher to explain the material to students, but first graders have a higher to play than learning, writing and reading. Therefore the teacher must be able to innovate in making props so that the

abstract can be explained with concrete objects so that students can play, but in fact they are learning, so students do not feel bored.

Based on the results of interviews with AR students on Tuesday, April 28, 2020 information was obtained that if the teacher taught using teaching aids he would become more focused and understand learning. Likewise the results of interviews with FW students on Wednesday, April 29, 2020 that when the teacher taught using teaching aids, he felt it was easier and understood what being learned.

This is also supported by the results of interviews with ZP students on Thursday, April 30, 2020 namely if the teacher teaches using teaching aids, learning will be more fun and easy to understand. This was also reinforced by the results of an interview with a student named AY on Thursday, April 30, 2020, namely that if the teacher taught using teaching aids, he felt it was easier to understand and more focused. Likewise, the results of an interview with a student named LV on Thursday, April 30, 2020 that the teacher taught using teaching aids, he felt more fun, easy to understand the lesson and more focused.

Based on the results of the interview above. It can be concluded that the use of teaching aids in the teaching and learning process can make learning more effective, easy to understand because you can see directly the example intended by the teacher.

Motivation to Learn

Based on the results of an interview with Mrs.JL, a grade 1B teacher at Elementary School 027 Samarinda Ulu on Monday, April 27, 2020 that the teacher had made a complete lesson schedule. In general, students obey school regulations. if there are students who get less grades then he tries to improve the less scores. Students are also enthusiastic about bringing props when asked by the teacher to bring them such as seeds and origami paper. In fact, not all students can seriously participate in learning, but when the teacher uses teaching aids, the students are more motivated to focus on learning. In general, grade 1B students have a high sense of competence with their peers to get the best results in class. Grade 1 students are very happy to get praise, so the teacher provides feedback in the form of rewards for students who excel. The rewards that are often given are in the form of speech and body language, such as the words great, smart, giving applause and thumbs up. As for the desire of students to go to school, there are students who

diligent and some are not diligent. In general, students in grade 1B who diligent can be categorized as students who go to school diligently.

Based on the results of interviews with AR, ZP, FW, AY and LV students. They recorded the lesson schedule given by the teacher and obeyed rules such as going to class on time. They improve their learning results if they get a score below average.

Based on the results of interviews with AR students on Tuesday, April 28, 2020, it was strengthened by the results of the FW interview on Wednesday, April 29, 2020. It was strengthened by the results of interviews with ZP students on Thursday, April 30, 2020 and also strengthened by the results of interviews with AY students on Thursday, April 30, 2020 was even strengthened by the results of interviews with LV students on Thursday, April 30, 2020 that teaching aids were provided by the teacher, there were also students who brought each one from home, such as seeds and origami paper. All students bring teaching aids ordered by the teacher.

Based on the results of interviews with class 1B students named AR, ZP, FW, AY, and LV, they are more serious about participating in learning activities when the teacher uses teaching aids. The seriousness they do by focusing on paying attention to the teacher's explanation and concentrating on learning activities. Based on the results of the interview, it was found that they were always trying to get the best results. The teacher gives praise when there are students who get the best results. His compliments are in the form of body language, such as applause and thumbs up. Grade 1B students are enthusiastic about coming to school and diligent in taking notes on the subject matter explained by the teacher

This is the same as the results of interviews with parents of students named Mrs. AT, Mrs. ER, Mrs. WI, and Mrs. SI on Wednesday, April 29, 2020 that their children have high aspirations to become teachers, doctors and others. Efforts made by his child to realize that is to repeat the lessons that have been learned in school. If it gets bad results he tries to fix it. They also always bring props from home when the teacher asks them to be serious in participating in classroom learning activities.

Based on the results of the document review found by researchers regarding student learning motivation. It was seen from the absence of students who were always present unless they were sick. Based on the results of the interview and review of the documents above, it was concluded that grade 1B students had good motivation

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the interviews and document review above, it can be concluded that the types of teaching aids used by the teacher are two-dimensional and three-dimensional visual types, namely pictures, origami paper, number cards and types of audio props. This is in accordance with the theory (Sumiharsono H. , 2017) that teaching aids are devices that can be seen by the eye and heard by the ear. The use of teaching aids by the teacher can increase student motivation. As explained in theory (Solichah, 2014) that the benefits of teaching aids in learning can make the teaching and learning process more motivated. Teachers and students, especially students, will feel happy, aroused, interested, and their interest and willingness to learn.

The learning motivation of grade 1B students is stated to be good, this can be proven by the willingness of students to provide teaching aids from home, such as carrying origami paper and carrying seeds. In addition, students efforts to improve unsatisfactory grades were evidenced by students asking questions about material that had not been understood and practicing doing questions given by the teacher. As for the focus of students during learning. It was proven by students listening, paying attention, and not talking or playing much during learning, as well as students who had material notes. Then, the enthusiasm of students in learning is evidenced by the presence of good students and the enthusiasm of students in demonstrating it directly. This is indicated by the results of collage work and flat shapes from origami paper made by students.

Student behavior above that reflects a motivated attitude is reinforced by the theory (Darmadi, 2017) that the form of individual behavior that has the characteristics of learning motivation can be seen from the seriousness of students in participating in learning. The desire of students to provide the tools or learning resources needed, the seriousness of students in listening. Teacher's explanation, efforts to get the best results and enthusiasm of students in following lessons.

Research conducted by researchers has proven that the use of teaching aids by teachers can increase student motivation. This is evidenced by the willingness of students to bring props, students's efforts to improve poor grades. Students are more focused during learning and students who are enthusiastic in learning and demonstrate directly the use of teaching aids. This is in accordance with research (Purbaningsih, 2017) with the title Use of Teaching Aids to Increase Motivation and Mathematics Learning

Outcomes of Class IV Students of SD Negeri 03 Gondangrejo in the 2017 academic year. That the use of teaching aids can increase student learning motivation can be seen from the characteristics of learning behavior. The student enthusiasm for learning, dare to answer questions in front of the class, are able to solve problems properly and correctly, are resilient and do not give up easily and diligent in learning.

The results of this study are also in accordance with the research (Widiastuti, 2016) entitled the use of folding paper teaching aids to increase student motivation and learning outcomes in mathematics in the fraction concept of class iv at Elementary School negeri 1 Harapan Rejo for the 2015/2016 Academic Year. folding paper props can increase student motivation and learning outcomes. The increase in student motivation can be seen from the interest and attention of students towards learning, the enthusiasm of students to do learning tasks, the responsibility of students in doing assignments and the reactions or responses shown by students to the assignments given by the teacher.

5 CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the discussion regarding the use of teaching aids in increasing student motivation at Elementary School 027 Samarinda, it was found that the teacher used teaching aids that were two-dimensional and three-dimensional. The increase in learning motivation of class 1B students is good. This is evidenced by the willingness of students to bring props, the enthusiasm of students in increasing the value that is lacking, the increase in student learning focus, the enthusiasm of students in directly demonstrating the teaching aids.

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